

Improving Underwater Object Detection with Cross-Media Communication

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Abstract— Underwater object detection increasingly relies on unmanned systems collecting significant sonar data, which is processed on board the vehicle. Connecting obtained insights require efficient transmission to a central processing unit. However, underwater acoustic communication suffers from limitations in bandwidth and latency compared to radio frequency communication. This work investigates the benefits of cross-media communication networks to utilize radio communication alongside acoustic transmission. A MATLAB network simulation was conducted to show the differences in the transmission behavior with and without cross-media communication. The results demonstrate that combining radio and acoustic communication can improve the coverage of underwater surveillance, as the data, through the gained multi-hop capability, can reach the central evaluation unit from greater distances.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sabotage of the Nord Stream gas pipelines has highlighted the fact that critical maritime infrastructure (CMI), including subsea energy assets, may be intentionally targeted amid geopolitical tensions and economic conflict [1]. At the same time, long-term national energy policies anticipate a significant increase in the number of offshore energy installations, with projected capacities of several tens of gigawatts expected by the mid-2040s. This development increases the need to protect offshore assets and operational processes against failure, external disturbances and intentional attacks [2]. To protect this MCI, it is necessary to monitor the situation below the water surface. Sonar systems are used for this purpose, which are capable of performing underwater object detection.

To perform underwater object detection, unmanned systems are being increasingly deployed [3]. These systems capture sonar data and process it on board to detect objects. To identify an object, it is necessary to combine information from different vehicles. Therefore all detections are transmitted to a central evaluation unit, which can be realized, for example, through a crewed platform or a land station. Data transmission underwater occurs via hydroacoustic signals. These are characterized by higher latencies and lower data rates compared to comparable protocols in electromagnetic transmission [4]. For this reason, data transmission can be improved by employing additional radio communication [5].

II. RELATED WORK

The limited transmission capabilities underwater are already the focus of various research projects [6]. To circumvent these limitations, there are approaches utilizing cross-media communication to shift message exchange to the

radio domain as much as possible [5]. The motivation for minimising underwater communication lies in the fundamental properties of hydroacoustic channels, where the overall latency of communication is determined not only by the process of transmitting data, but also by the way signals propagate over distance. Since acoustic signals travel much more slowly in water than radio signals in air, propagation delays become a dominant factor, especially in spatially extended offshore scenarios [7]. This shift reduces the impact of distance-dependent acoustic delays, enabling shorter connection establishment times and improving the overall reliability of data transmission.

Based on the available test data collected within the “Industrielle Räumung von Altlasten in Verklappungsgebieten” (IRAV) project [8], detection result data packets have a size of 1-30 kB. Such data volumes can already pose a challenge for the acoustic communication channel [4]. As underwater object detection is performed simultaneously by multiple systems, coordinating data transmission for evaluation also presents a challenge. Collisions on the channel lead to further delays in transmissions. These can be prevented or resolved using Medium Access (MAC) Protocols such as Carrier Sense Multiple Access/Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA) or Listen Before Talk (LBT) [9]. However, even in the event of a collision, the transmission is still significantly delayed due to the slow signal propagation underwater. This communication needs to be improved through the use of a cross-media network.

In recent years, various approaches have emerged to enable communication between participants above and below the water surface in a network. The network layer poses a particular challenge in multi-domain underwater and surface networks, as routing decisions must cope with highly dynamic topologies, distance-dependent delays and fluctuating link quality. This requires adaptive strategies to maintain reliable end-to-end communication [10]. Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are widely used in maritime and multi-domain scenarios thanks to their decentralised nature and suitability for dynamic environments. Routing protocols are usually categorised as either proactive or reactive, depending on whether routes are continuously maintained or only established when needed [11].

In terrestrial environments, well-established mobile ad hoc network routing protocols, such as the Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) protocol, offer reactive, proactive and hybrid routing approaches [12].

Typically, these protocols rely on periodic control messages, such as HELLO messages, to maintain an up-to-date view of the network topology and detect link failures in dynamic, radio-based networks. They are therefore optimised for high-bandwidth wireless communication, rapidly changing topologies and low-latency information exchange.

In contrast, the underwater domain commonly employs routing protocols such as Depth-Based Routing (DBR), which are specifically designed for hydroacoustic communication and its inherent constraints, including high latency, limited bandwidth and strict energy efficiency requirements [13]. Consequently, underwater routing protocols are often classified as data-centric, flooding-based or geographic-based approaches. In addition to domain-specific routing protocols, the first cross-domain approaches have been suggested to facilitate the forwarding of data between underwater, surface and aerial nodes. These approaches typically combine hierarchical routing and clustering mechanisms to relay information across communication domains and often assume known node positions and predefined communication ranges [14].

Another approach for cross-media communication is an extension of the AODV protocol, which uses passive approaches for topology management. In Extended AODV, it is possible to implement data transmissions from UUV to Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), which would contribute to the improvement of underwater object detection. In this approach, route establishment works via route requests and ping messages. A UUV sends a Route Request (RREQ) to check if the destination is within direct range. Therefore, RREQs are not forwarded underwater compared to classic AODV.

If the destination does not respond, a "PING" is sent as a broadcast, to which all possible USVs respond, as they can be reached both acoustically and via radio, and can therefore transfer the communication to the more performant radio channel. Upon receiving the first "PING," the UUV responds with a unicast "PING" to the origin. The addressed Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV), upon receipt, initiates the classic route establishment according to AODV and reports back to the UUV after successful establishment. Then the route is established and data packets can be exchanged. If a route becomes invalid due to movement of the nodes, this is detected in a reactive concept through hybrid passive acknowledgment. This requires significantly fewer control messages, freeing up more capacity on the channel for useful data. For this reason, Extended AODV is being considered for underwater object detection.

Previous studies have shown that Extended AODV is characterized by lower utilization of the acoustic channel in a cross-media network [5]. However, these studies have focused only on control messages and network management. This paper examines the effects of using Extended AODV on payload transmission

III. SCENARIO DEFINITION

When an Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) is used for object detection, the resulting total sonar data is first processed due to its size, in order to obtain the mentioned 1-30 kB of data to be transmitted per evaluation. To define the process of underwater object detection, the IRUV project is chosen as a reference. In this project, the UUV records sonar data over a distance of 50 m to perform a single evaluation.

This results in a data packet of 1-30 kB every 50 m, which must be transmitted to the central control unit. Since this data accumulates over missions of possibly several hours, and due to the limited transmission capabilities of the acoustic channel, it is not sent directly. The data is buffered and the transmission process is only started upon completion of the mission or when the memory is full. For this purpose, the UUV surfaces and sends the data via the radio channel to the control unit. This process is not suitable for scenarios involving the protection of MCI. Results during the mission should be sent directly to the central control unit upon generation, in order to keep the periods without monitoring as short as possible. Surfacing is also undesirable, as it requires additional time and leads to gaps in observation.

To combine the described concepts, a scenario needs to be defined with which the change in performance indicators can be evaluated. The observation of an open area is defined. The scaling is set to 2000 m * 2000 m. In this area, two UUVs and one USV, which represents the central evaluation unit, are positioned. The UUVs are located at a depth of 20 m. The UUVs execute a mission depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2 at a speed of 2 m/s and send a 2 kB data packet to the USV every 50 m. With the given path, this results in a duration of 79 minutes. This scenario is considered in two versions. The first version represents the baseline without multi-hop capability. The data is sent to the USV regardless of position and reachability. In the second version, Extended AODV is used, as well as two additional USVs are added to establish the multi-hop capability. In both versions, it is considered how many data packets are sent during a mission run and how many reach the central control unit. The assumed ranges and frequencies are 1800 m and 2.4 GHz for radio and 1000 m and 18-34 kHz for acoustics. The ranges, which are directly related to the frequency, have been determined empirically.

Figure 1 – Mission Path of the scenario for underwater object detection in an area of 2000 m * 2000 m

Figure 2 - side view of the participants in the scenarios. 2 USV are added in multi hop scenario to extend the possible communication range

IV. SIMULATION

A MATLAB network simulation models a setup for the transmission of detection result data from unmanned systems. The network simulation is an extension of simpleMANET into the three-dimensional domain and includes a hydroacoustic communication channel. The developments needed for a cross-media network simulator are integrated into the preexisting simpleMANET and were first presented in earlier studies [5]. The simulator employs a deterministic, time-discrete architecture that supports repeatable, domain-specific evaluations. The experimental configuration was implemented to measure the performance and effectiveness of developed communication mechanisms in the hybrid network setting.

At each simulated time step, every participant in the network checks whether they need to send a message in accordance with the scenario or the embedded protocol. Upon transmission of a message across a designated communication channel, the system determines the recipients of the packet and calculates the duration of the transmission based on the distance between the nodes. Other physical circumstances are not currently taken into account at the network layer.

One participant in the network is defined as the central evaluation unit. Further UUV are positioned in the scenario and transmit data packets to the evaluation unit. The data consists of available test data. The size and frequency of the data are considered, but not the content itself. This is contrasted with an extended scenario. In this scenario, additional USV are used as hops on the data route. This means that in the extended scenario, the data is not sent directly to the evaluation unit, but first to a corresponding USV.

V. RESULTS

The results of the two scenario versions obtained from the simulation are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Data traffic occurring in the scenario per version generated from the MATLAB network simulation

It can be seen that more data arrives at the central control unit in the multi-hop capable version. However, the total data traffic on the network is increased due to the multi-hop behavior.

In both versions, 397 data packets are sent. The additional data traffic in the multi-hop version can be explained by the Extended AODV protocol. Route establishment, route management, and packet forwarding increase this value.

However, this overhead ensures that all sent data packets reach their destination.

It is noticeable that the majority of data packets reach their destination via the radio channel. This is because, in the reactive approach of Extended AODV, routes are only rebuilt when they become invalid. That is, once a route is established via the radio channel, it is used throughout the entire mission. Even if the sender and receiver are within direct range, this does not change.

In the single-hop version, no radio traffic occurs, as only one participant has a radio interface. The acoustic traffic is also lower, as the overhead of Extended AODV is eliminated. In addition to the sent data packets, only the acknowledgements from the receiver occur. However, since there is no range extension through multi-hop capability, only 66 % of the data packets reach their destination.

With 397 data packets of 2 kB each (2048 bytes), 813,056 bytes of payload are generated. In the multi-hop version, a total of 1,594,048 bytes are sent. The payload proportion of the traffic is therefore approximately 51 %. In the single-hop version, a total of 833,246 bytes are sent. The payload proportion is therefore approximately 97 %.

The higher channel utilization due to the overhead of Extended AODV is the disadvantage, but it achieves the advantage that 100 % instead of 66 % of the data packets reach their destination.

As a side effect, the need for retransmission due to channel collisions can be reduced. If two UUVs are within range of a reachable USV, the USV cannot receive two simultaneous transmissions from the UUVs. However, the UUVs may not be within each other's reception range, meaning the collision would go unnoticed. By deploying additional USVs, these can be used as hops, shifting the communication to the radio channel. Collisions can also occur in the radio channel, but these can be resolved with a significantly shorter delay with state of the art MAC-Protocols. This behavior is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – topology of the multi-hop version showing that collisions of acoustic signals can happen without the senders noticing

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

By utilizing Extended AODV and two additional hops, the data transmission rate in underwater object detection can be increased by 34 %. Data packets reach the central control unit via the hop, even if no direct connection exists. The disadvantage is a higher utilization of both communication channels. However, since the performant transmission of

detection results underwater is a priority in this consideration, the solution can be considered successful.

However, the scenario considered in this work should be understood as an example. In further considerations, it is necessary to validate the results with changed parameters. The impact of packet size, transmission rates, or the dimension and number of participants on the results must be investigated. A practical validation is also still pending. In addition, a comparison between the Extended AODV used here and other cross-media routing protocols would be useful.

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